

The HPR1000 Core Physics Computation System and Its Application in Teaching

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ABSTRACT

Traditional nuclear engineering education faces persistent challenges, including high cost, high risk, substantial resource consumption, and difficulties in implementing, observing, and reproducing reactor core processes. To address these limitations, Tsinghua University, in collaboration with the Nuclear Power Institute of China, developed a core physics computation and visualization system based on the physical characteristics of the domestically developed Generation-III nuclear power technology "HPR1000." The system integrates a nodal-method solver with a high-fidelity three-dimensional post-processing module and provides four major computational functions: burnup calculation, state-change analysis, control-rod bank movement simulation, and xenon evolution modeling. These functions enable students to intuitively observe reactor core behavior and understand the key physical responses of the core under different conditions. Teaching experience indicates that the system effectively improves students' grasp of reactor-physics principles, supports the development of analytical skills, and enhances overall engagement during experimental courses. Students benefit from being able to visualize reactor behavior directly, interact with multiple operating scenarios, and connect theoretical knowledge with practical core physics phenomena. The core physics computation system provides a safe, efficient, and accessible digital teaching platform for cultivating new-generation nuclear engineering professionals, supporting the growing demand for skilled professionals in China's nuclear power sector.

Keywords: HPR1000; reactor core physics; virtual simulation; nuclear engineering education; visualization system

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global nuclear power industry has continued to develop rapidly. By the end of 2024, 31 countries generated electricity using nuclear power. There were 440 operational nuclear power units worldwide, providing 2,667 TWh of electricity, which accounts for approximately a quarter of the world's low-carbon electricity [1].

As one of the countries with the fastest nuclear power development, China has been actively promoting the strategy of nuclear power autonomy and has successfully developed the third-generation pressurized water reactor nuclear power technology with complete independent intellectual property rights - "Hualong One" (HPR1000). This technology was jointly developed by China National Nuclear Corporation (CNNC) and China General Nuclear Power Corporation (CGN). It is equipped with a combined passive and active safety system, which can automatically activate the cooling mechanism in emergency situations to ensure core safety and fully meet the highest

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international safety standards. A schematic diagram of the active and passive safety systems is shown in Figure 1, reprinted from Ref.[2].

Figure 1. Schematic diagrams of the active and passive safety systems in HPR1000

As of 2025, China has 58 nuclear power units in operation, with a total installed capacity of approximately 60.91 million kilowatts. Another 54 units are under construction or under approval, with an installed capacity of approximately 64.46 million kilowatts [3]. With the rapid development of nuclear power, the demand for high-quality nuclear power professionals is becoming increasingly urgent [4].

However, traditional nuclear engineering education has long been constrained by the high capital investment required for experimental facilities, the inherent radiological hazards associated with student operational errors, and the intensive resource consumption (both energy and manpower) involved in long-term reactor maintenance. Furthermore, technical challenges such as the difficulty of real-time observation and the irreducibility of complex transient processes within physical cores have significantly hindered pedagogical effectiveness and the efficiency of talent cultivation. Internationally, many universities have implemented virtual simulation programs in nuclear engineering. Representative examples include the Department of Nuclear Engineering at the Polytechnic University of Madrid in Spain [5], Linnaeus University in Sweden [6], the Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the United States [7], and the Department of Nuclear Engineering, North Carolina State University [8]. Universities in China are also actively promoting the digital transformation of nuclear engineering education [9]. For instance, Tsinghua University has developed high-temperature gas-cooled reactor teaching software eHTR [10], CP1000s, sodium-cooled fast reactor teaching software eCFR [11], as well as a virtual simulation teaching network platform for nuclear engineering [12]. Xi'an Jiaotong University has developed the nusolsim software for simulating abnormal conditions such as main circuit flow [13]; Sun Yat-sen University is exploring the application of digital twin technology in nuclear engineering teaching [14]; Virtual Simulation Teaching Experiment of Fission Reactors, University of Science and Technology of China and Virtual Simulation Laboratory for the China Fusion Engineering Test Reactor [15]. However, the current virtual simulation systems in university teaching mainly focus on the overall operation or accident scenarios of nuclear power plants. The simulation of the internal physical processes of the reactor core is still insufficient, especially lacking detailed simulation of key physical issues such as the evolution of fuel consumption, xenon poisoning kinetics, and the effective length distribution of control rods.

To address this issue, the Virtual Simulation Laboratory for Nuclear Engineering at Tsinghua University, in collaboration with the China National Nuclear Corporation, developed a dedicated core physics computation and visualization system based on the actual physical characteristics of the HPR1000 reactor core. The system employs immersive and interactive 3D visualization techniques, allowing students to intuitively and safely explore the reactor's internal structure and its complex physical processes. It effectively addresses the problems of "invisibility, inaccessibility, and difficulty in understanding" inherent in traditional teaching, infusing nuclear engineering education with digital and intelligent innovation. To maintain pedagogical focus, the system is dedicated to core-level physics and thermal-hydraulic coupling, rather than the entire balance of plant.

2. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

2.1. System Architecture

The HPR1000 reactor core physics computation system consists of two parts: the nodal-method-solver-core and the three-dimensional high-precision post-processing module. The solver models the actual reactor core structure of HPR1000, including 177 fuel assemblies and 157 control rods, and supports the calculation of three-dimensional power and burnup distributions at the pin-by-pin and fuel assembly levels, as well as functions such as state-change analysis, burnup calculation, xenon evolution calculation, and 3D data post-processing (as shown in Figure 2). The solver employs a two-step calculation scheme to balance computational efficiency and precision. Initially, homogenized few-group constants are generated through lattice transport calculations. Subsequently, the core simulator solves the three-dimensional two-group neutron diffusion equations using the Nodal Expansion Method (NEM). Thermal-hydraulic feedback is integrated by accounting for variations in fuel temperature and moderator density, which are coupled with the neutronic solver to update macroscopic cross-sections and ensure physical consistency.

Figure 2. System Framework

2.2. Solver

The core physical computation system of HPR1000 reactor is a lightweight program optimized specifically for educational scenarios. This system achieves a balance between computational efficiency and interactive response speed while maintaining the key physical models for engineering analysis. Through power and fuel consumption reconfiguration technology, the system supports obtaining detailed power and fuel consumption distribution data at the individual fuel assembly level, and can obtain calculation results matching the latest state at any fuel consumption time point by adjusting core state parameters.

Its core functions revolve around four typical reactor core physics problems, including control rod bank movement calculation, state-change analysis, burnup calculation, and xenon evolution calculation. The main functions of each module are as follows:

- (1) Control rod assembly movement calculation (RodPosition): This module simulates the insertion and withdrawal operations of individual control rod assemblies (RCCA) or selected control-rod clusters in a pressurized water reactor. Users can specify the insertion steps of each control rod assembly in the reactor core view, and combine conditions such as boron concentration, xenon equilibrium state, power reconfiguration options, and thermal parameters. The system automatically calculates the corresponding k_{eff} , reactivity changes, axial/radial power offsets, and relative power distribution of each fuel assembly. This function visually presents core concepts such as control-rod worth, shutdown depth, and power distortion, and is a key experimental tool for teaching reactivity control and operational safety.
- (2) State-Change Analysis (ChangeStatus): Modify some reactor core parameters (relative power, core pressure, inlet temperature, xenon state, boron concentration, control rod group positions, etc.) and perform the reactor-core physics calculations. After modification, the solver re-solves the neutron diffusion equation and outputs the physical field under the new steady state.
- (3) Burnup Calculation (CoreBurn): By adjusting the boron concentration and completing the burnup calculation, obtain the time-varying reactor core power distribution, burnup depth distribution, and nuclear density distribution of important nuclides. This module is used to explain engineering issues such as fuel cycle, reactivity consumption, and refueling strategy.
- (4) Xenon Evolution Modeling (TransXenon): For the I-Xe decay chain, a set of time-dependent burnup differential equations is established. Users can set multiple time steps (such as 0h, 4h, 10h, and 24h after shutdown) and specify the power level and control rod status at each step. The system then calculates the dynamic changes in iodine and xenon concentrations, with particular attention to the xenon peak after shutdown and its impact on restart capability. This function directly corresponds to the "iodine pit" phenomenon in nuclear power plant operation and is a key topic in reactor kinetics teaching.

2.3. Post-processing

Based on the front-end and back-end processing platform, a dedicated high-precision post-processing function module has been developed for the calculation results output by the solver. The post-processing module directly parses the output HDF5 result data and constructs a high-fidelity three-dimensional visualization mesh model, allowing users to intuitively grasp the spatial distribution law of the physical field of the current design scheme's calculation data.

3. THE APPLICATION OF HPR1000 CORE PHYSICS COMPUTATION SYSTEM IN NUCLEAR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Through the physical computation system of the HPR1000 reactor core, students can gain an in-depth and intuitive understanding of the changes in the reactor core during its operation.

Take the fuel burnup experiment as an example. During the operation of a nuclear reactor, the fuel constantly undergoes fission, leading to the gradual consumption of fissile nuclides such as uranium-235, while generating new nuclides like plutonium-239 and fission products (such as xenon-135 and samarium-149). This process is called Burnup and is the core physical process that determines the reactor's lifespan, power distribution, and refueling strategy. In traditional teaching, the concept of fuel burnup is often described in words or presented through simple curves, making it difficult for students to establish spatial cognition. The fuel burnup calculation module (CoreBurn) of the HPR1000 core physical computation system is based on the real core structure of HPR1000 and supports full-core time-step simulation, enabling students to "witness" the entire evolution of a core from its initial state to complete fuel burnup in a virtual environment.

Under the guidance of the teacher, students can use the software to complete the fuel burnup calculation. First, students need to open the fuel burnup module (as shown in Figure 3-a). After entering the "Fuel Burnup Data Input Panel", they can adjust the boron concentration, k_{eff} target value, burnup steps, and feedback mode (as shown in Figure 3-b). In the burnup steps setting, the number of burnup steps can be entered. Click the "OK" button to ensure that the input line number of the control rod group's positions (the control rod positions are given according to the proposed step) is updated. After the input is completed, the fuel burnup calculation can be carried out. The fuel burnup calculation was completed to obtain the core power distribution, fuel burnup depth distribution, and nuclear density distribution of important nuclides that vary with time. After the calculation is completed, students can view the two-dimensional results (as shown in Figure 4-a) and the three-dimensional results (as shown in Figure 4-b). It can be seen that in the three-dimensional power distribution graph, the colors represent the relative power density. The blue area represents the peripheral components with lower power, the yellow/orange area represents the central area with higher power, and the red area indicates that local hotspots may occur in the high-enrichment area. The two-dimensional figure shows the power distribution of the horizontal cross-section of the reactor core. The horizontal and vertical axes represent the positions of the fuel assembly (columns A-R, rows 01-15), and the color depth of each cell represents the average power of this assembly. Through this experiment, students can transform from the abstract concept of "fuel burnup" to a three-dimensional field distribution that can be seen and touched, and master how to identify potential hotspots through visualization.

(a) Computing Group interface

(b) Burnup data input panel

Figure 3. Operation interface

(a) 2D output parameter display interface

(b) 3D output parameter display interface

Figure 4. Output parameter interface

Similar to the fuel burnup calculation module, students can also complete state-change calculations under the guidance of their teachers. The parameters that can be changed in a variable state include relative power, thermohydraulic parameters (core inlet temperature, pressure, inlet flow rate, bypass flow), boron concentration, xenon concentration (equilibrium xenon, maximum xenon, fixed xenon, zero xenon), control rod group rod position, and rod adjustment steps.

In the overall parameter input of the reactor core, if the inlet temperature option is "Input multiple temperatures", the "Custom Inlet Temperature" button will be activated. Clicking it will pop up the inlet temperature input interface (as shown in Figure 5-a). The default display of the reactor core loading diagram is "all reactor cores", and the view can be switched through the drop-down menu. A certain component can be selected to change its temperature (as shown in Figure 5-b).

(a) Inlet temperature input panel

(b) State change calculation with different inlet temperatures

Figure 5. State change calculation input

In addition, students can export up to 170 types of detailed physical parameter data, covering core reactivity, burnup evolution, isotope number density, power distribution, thermal-hydraulics, control-

rod worth, and fission product behavior. These high-dimensional and high-precision data provide a robust basis for understanding reactor dynamics and enable data-driven research. By applying AI techniques such as machine learning, deep neural networks, or reinforcement learning, students can model large datasets to predict xenon oscillations, optimize fuel management, develop surrogate models, and explore digital-twin applications in nuclear engineering education. The integration of simulation and AI deepens students' understanding of reactor physics and enhances their capability to address complex engineering problems.

4. PRACTICAL EFFECTS IN TEACHING

To test the pedagogical effectiveness of the HPR1000 core physics computation system, the Virtual Simulation Laboratory of Nuclear Engineering at Tsinghua University carried out teaching activities in the undergraduate experimental courses in 2025 and collected and sorted out students' usage experiences and feedback.

This experimental course mainly imparts knowledge related to reactor physics to students and teaches them how to use the core physics calculation software of HPR1000. Under the guidance of the teacher, students completed the operation tasks of four modules in sequence: from setting the burnup steps size and boron adjustment strategy to simulating the xenon gas evolution after the reactor shutdown; and from adjusting the inlet temperature of local components to precisely controlling the positions of individual control rods. The entire process emphasizes a closed-loop learning model of "hands-on practice - observation - analysis - reflection". Students not only mastered the software operation process but also could intuitively experience the complex physical field evolution laws inside the reactor core through the 3D visualization results. During the experiment, the students demonstrated a strong interest in learning and proposed many innovative ideas. Among the 60 feedback responses received, most participants agreed that the software deepened their understanding of reactor physics. Compared with traditional teaching methods, this virtual simulation approach exhibited significantly higher teaching effectiveness and engagement (as shown in Figure 6). Students particularly highlighted that the intuitive interface and 3D visualization improved accessibility and learning efficiency, enabling them to grasp abstract physical laws more rapidly than through traditional derivations. This confirmed that the system effectively enhances students' spatial cognition while maintaining high learning motivation.

Figure 6. Feedback on Teaching Effectiveness

5. CONCLUSIONS

The HPR1000 core physics computation system is an important carrier for extending China's independent innovation achievements in nuclear power to higher education, successfully achieving a deep integration of "real reactor parameters, real physical models, and real engineering logic" with classroom teaching.

The system not only alleviates the long-standing challenges of high cost, high risk, and high resource consumption in nuclear engineering education, but also significantly enhances students' understanding of reactor-core physical processes and their engineering reasoning skills through immersive, interactive, and visualized teaching methods.

Practice has shown that the core physics computation system of HPR1000 has initially established a new teaching path from theoretical instruction to virtual practice, and from knowledge acquisition to problem exploration, providing strong support for cultivating new era nuclear power talents with solid professional foundations and cutting-edge technical literacy. In the future, with the further integration of technologies such as artificial intelligence and digital twins, such dedicated simulation platforms will play an even more crucial role in the digital transformation of nuclear engineering education.

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